

IMPORTANCE OF DRAWING IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONS IN SOCIETY

Dr. Sudha Jain ^{*1}

^{*1} Assistance Professor, (Social work) Indore School of Social Work, Indore

Abstract

Drawing is used to express one's creativity, and therefore has been prominent in the world of art. Throughout much of history, drawing was regarded as the foundation for artistic practice. Initially, artists used and reused wooden tablets for the production of their drawings. Following the widespread availability of paper in the 14th century, the use of drawing in the arts increased. At this point, drawing was commonly used as a tool for thought and investigation, acting as a study medium whilst artists were preparing for their final pieces of work. The Renaissance brought about a great sophistication in drawing techniques, enabling artists to represent things more realistically than before, [and revealing an interest in geometry and philosophy.

The invention of the first widely available form of photography led to a shift in the hierarchy of the arts. Photography offered an alternative to drawing as a method for accurately representing visual phenomena, and traditional drawing practice was given less emphasis as an essential skill for artists, particularly so in Western society. The 14th century, the use of drawing in the arts increased. At this point, drawing was commonly used as a tool for thought and investigation, acting as a study medium whilst artists were preparing for their final pieces of work. The Renaissance brought about a great sophistication in drawing techniques, enabling artists to represent things more realistically than before, and revealing an interest in geometry and philosophy. It plays very important role in development of persons in society.

Keywords: Drawing; Society; Development.

Cite This Article: Dr. Sudha Jain. (2019). "IMPORTANCE OF DRAWING IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONS IN SOCIETY." *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 7(11SE), 99-103. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3585081>.

1. Introduction

Importance of Drawing

Drawing is a visual art. It connects a person with so many things. Through drawing, a person can achieve following aspects. These aspects are very much useful in ones socio- psycho development. These aspects are as follows:

1. Visualization

Drawing helps us to map out mental images of the world we see around us. This is helpful for numerous reasons. We can map out plans, diagrams, and concepts for what we want to bring into the world, or we can make images of how a system works. Visual aids often help us comprehend large amounts of data that our brain cannot understand through numbers or words alone. On the more emotional side, drawing allows the creator to open one's expressive vents and let emotion become recorded in the marks of your drawing. Often feelings are too complex for us to understand, and art helps record and express them.

2. Coordination

Drawing is the skill, which helps in coordination. One can coordinate and compare situation, events and problems through drawing.

3. Cerebral Benefits

In today's world, it is so easy to be distracted by social media and our digital devices. Our brains get a temporary endorphin release from these diversions, and it is easy to devote a large amount of time to them. Unfortunately, this can make us less industrious in our free time. Drawing is a great release, and because we are using our brain while we are drawing, we build new connections and pathways in our brain. Both sides of the brain actively participate, as the left side is responsible for logical thinking and the right supplies the creativity. As a result, our brains grow.

4. Analytical Skills

When drawing, whether consciously or not, we are making decisions about what we are depicting. This improves decision-making skills and helps with problem solving. If a drawing is not going the way it was intended, an artist has to be able to step back and make rational decisions about how to fix it.

5. Concentration

It is usually safe to say that if we are not doodling absentmindedly while on the phone, that we are focused on a drawing. If you want your drawing to go the way you intend, you need to focus on what is going on in your drawing and what you are looking at. If you are drawing from life, you want to be present in the moment, and record the beauty of everything that is going on around you. The relationship between you and the subject matter is one of the most important parts of what is going on in the piece.

6. Understanding

Drawing allows us to better understand our subject matter. That understanding could be the form of the object, the gentle curve of a line, or how we feel and respond to whatever the subject matter is. The more you draw something, the more you remember it and know it. Our minds begin to grasp more of what it really is rather than our conceptual symbols of it.

7. Developing an “eye”

Some people believe that artists “see” differently. This may or may not be true, but those who draw from life regularly are practiced in noticing proportions, relationships, and compositions. They are often good judges of tonal relationships, as well as of measurements and distances.

8. Communication

Drawing is a tool for communication. Sometime it is not possible to interact. Under such circumstances, drawing is very much helpful. Drawing becomes source of communication.

9. Mental Attitude

Some people feel most at ease when drawing. It is often used for therapy and stress relief. Creating something from nothing also makes us feel productive, and that helps us feel good about ourselves. Being present in the moment and focused during a drawing session can be a feeling akin to meditation. We only get down on ourselves during a drawing if we let our ego get in the way and try to compete with others or ourselves.

10. Pleasure

What could be better than being able to fill an empty page and bring our thoughts and musings to life? Drawing is fun, and should be enjoyed by children. It gives immense pleasure to the person who is using it.

2. Drawing Helps in Development of Children

Drawing is a type of art, which is not important only for adults but also for children. Children can learn even very difficult thing in easy way through drawing skills. If they will see drawing of any topic then they easily understand concept of that topic. Children get help in following manner through drawing:

Develops Fine Motor Skills

Fine motor skills include any specialized movement of the hands, wrists, and fingers. As an adult, you rely on fine motor skills when you type, drive, or even text. It’s important for your child to develop strong fine motor skills at a young age. Holding and manipulating writing implements represents one of the best ways to improve a child’s fine motor skills. Drawing creates immediate visual feedback that changes depending on the tool your child uses and how he or she uses it. This feedback helps your child identify the best ways to produce the desired result.

Encourages Visual Analysis

Young children do not yet understand some concepts that you may take for granted, such as distance, size comparison, and textural differences. Drawing provides the perfect opportunity for your child to learn these concepts in a deliberate way. Having a child draw specific items, especially in relationship to each other, can help him or her perform fundamental visual analysis

of everyday spaces. To support this kind of drawing at home, prompt your child to draw examples of big and small, rough and smooth, far and near, and so on.

Helps Establish Concentration

Because most children enjoy drawing, this activity provides time to establish the concepts of concentration and practice. These concepts will be essential to your child's academic success, even in elementary school. Learning how to observe small details, concentrate on achieving a specific result, and practice tricky tasks helps your child mature.

Improves Hand-Eye Coordination

In addition to improving fine motor skills, drawing enables your child to draw connections between what he or she sees and what he or she does. This hand-eye coordination is important in athletic and recreational situations, as well as in academic scenarios such as penmanship lessons. For a hand-eye coordination boost, have your child draw an object while looking at it or copy a drawing that you made.

Increases Individual Confidence

As a parent or guardian, you probably love to hear the phrase, "Look what I made!" When you child has an opportunity to create physical representations of his or her imagination, thoughts, and experiences, he or she gains confidence. Drawing can help your child feel more intrinsic motivation, self-worth, and validity. This affirmation will make him or her more confident in other areas that may not come as naturally as drawing.

Teaches Creative Problem Solving

Along with visual analysis and concentration, drawing encourages your child to solve problems creatively. When he or she draws, your child must determine the best way to connect body parts, portray emotions, and depict specific textures. Providing specific drawing tasks, such as creating a family portrait, and talking about your child's color, method, or special choices can help him or her develop stronger problem solving skills over time. To help your child feel motivated to draw and create, use positive reinforcement. You may want to display finished drawings in your child's room or in other areas of your home, include personalized drawings in letters to family members, and praise your child for practice and specific achievements.

3. Drawing in Science

Drawing has also been used extensively in the field of science, as a method of discovery, understanding and explanation. Drawing has also been used extensively in the field of science, as a method of discovery, understanding and explanation. Drawing diagrams of observations is an important part of scientific study. In 1609, astronomer Galileo Galilee explained the changing phases of Venus and the sunspots through his observational telescopic drawings. In 1924, geophysicist Alfred Wegener used illustrations to visually demonstrate the origin of the continents.

4. Conclusion

Drawing as artistic expression, it is a natural behavior, just as language is a natural behavior of expressing oneself, so is art. When children are young, they draw to express themselves. They try to draw something creative that reflects their thought process.

There are different types of language. You might not understand a particular language. However, art is a universal form of communication. Everyone can understand it. With drawing art, you can share your ideas and thoughts with other people.

When we look at the paintings made in caves and rocks by the ancient people, it gives us an idea about their culture. Therefore, drawing art is a form of preserving culture. It reflects a society's beliefs, cultural values, etc. People visit many places because of art, like the Louvre in Paris or Granville Island in Vancouver. Art does not only mean expensive things; these are architecture and sculpture as well. Like writing, it can show what is, or what if, but drawing is nonverbal so it appeals to its own areas of the mind. The aphorism is that it is like a thousand words. It may show up in advertising as a quick stereotype. Or it could be a statement in graffiti. It can be practical like a map or aesthetic like a work of art. It shows differences between cultures. There are many styles through the centuries. It is an exercise of the imagination.

Bibliography

- [1] Robinson, A (2009). Writing and script: a very short introduction. New York: Oxford University Press.
- [2] Kovats, T (2005). The Drawing Book. London: Black Dog Publishing.
- [3] Walker, J. F; Duff, L; Davies, J (2005). "Old Manuals and New Pencils". Drawing- The Process. Bristol: Intellect Books.
- [4] van de Wetering, Ernst. Rembrandt: The Painter at Work.
- [5] Chamberlain, R (2013). "Drawing Conclusions: An exploration of the cognitive and neuroscientific foundations of representational drawing".
- [6] Davis, P; Duff, L; Davies, J (2005). "Drawing a Blank". Drawing – The Process. Bristol: Intellect Books. pp. 15–25.
- [7] Simmons, S (2011). "Philosophical Dimension of Drawing Instruction"
- [8] Poe, E. A. (1840). The Daguerreotype. Classic Essays on Photography. New Haven, CN: Leete's Island Books. pp. 37–3
- [9] Ruskin, J. (1857). The Elements of Drawing. Mineola, NY: Dover Publications Inc. ISBN 978-1-4538-4264-5Spears, Heather.
- [10] The Creative Eye. London: Arcturus. 2007. ISBN 978-0-572-03315-6.
- [11] Drawing/Thinking: Confronting an Electronic Age, edited by Marc Treib, 2008, ISBN 0-415-77
- [12] Drawing/Thinking: Confronting an Electronic Age, edited by Marc Treib, 2008, ISBN 0-415-77560-4